

NET-Fuels deliverable report

NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 | GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101083780

Deliverable D4.4:

Studying NET-Fuels impact in the society

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	x

Document Type		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x

Due Date: 28/02/2026 (Month 40)
Submission date: 28/02/2026
Reference Period: 01/06/2024 – 28/02/2026
Deliverable Lead Partner: University of Bologna (UNIBO)
Contributing partners (If applicable): All partners

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

General Information

GA Number: 101083780
Start date of project: 01/11/2022
Project Duration: 4 years
Project website: <https://netfuelsproject.org/>

NET-Fuels consortium

Short	Beneficiary	Role
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	CO
FRA	Fraunhofer UMSICHT	BEN
LEITAT	Acondicionamiento Tarrasense (LEITAT)	BEN
SUT	Silesian University of Technology	BEN
ITHAKA	Ithaka Institute	BEN
REACH	REACH Innovation	BEN
WRG	WRG Europe	AP

CO...Coordinator, BEN...Beneficiary, AP...Associated Partner

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.4 presents a prospective, economy-wide assessment of the impacts associated with the deployment and scale-up of the NET-Fuels technology in the EU for 2030 and 2050 scenarios. The analysis is based on an environmentally extended input-output framework using the EXIOBASE3 database, which provides coverage of inter-industry relationships, environmental emissions, material and resource flows, and employment by skill level and gender across multiple regions. The modelling framework connects NET-Fuels products and processes to corresponding products, sectors, and end uses, enabling the quantification of direct and indirect effects through the economy.

A dynamic and scenario-based approach is applied to simulate the gradual penetration of NET-Fuels in the energy and fuel market, under alternative expansion levels and feedstock availability constraints. Maximum and minimum expansion scenarios are defined using the upper bound of treatable residual biomass availability provided within the project and technical capacity. These bounds are used as limiting conditions for industry expansion and for estimating the corresponding range of economic value generated in Exiobase sectors.

The innovation of such assessment lies in combining technology-specific process data provided by the Consortium partners with an environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE-MRIO) model processing EXIOBASE3 dataset and using hybrid IO-LCA integration. Adding on the evaluation of NET-Fuels as an isolated plant-level system in other tasks of the project, this framework applies a consequential, prospective approach. NET-Fuels is introduced as generator of new product flows, mapped to IO sectors, with explicit substitution of conventional fuels and products and subsequently scaled-up to 2030 and 2050 scenarios. Direct and indirect ripple effects on the economic system are assessed across EU and global supply chains, including output reallocation, emissions, material and resource use, and employment.

Sectoral output results show a targeted reallocation rather than a generalized contraction. In 2030, early deployment (27 plants, 140 kt/y feedstock each) generates measurable but still limited expansion in NF-related activities, while fossil sectors begin to contract (e.g., natural gas extraction and related services). By 2050, with large-scale deployment, structural effects become pronounced. These gains are counterbalanced by reductions concentrated in fossil-related and linked upstream sectors. The magnitude of change increases with the deployment scale of NF capacity and substitution of fossil-based products. In absolute monetary values, the global system contracts by -1.700 M€ in 2030 and by around $30\,000$ M€ by 2050 compared to future scenarios without NET-Fuels (noNF).

Regarding absolute emissions, an increase from 2020 to 2030 and 2050 in baseline scenarios happens due to overall economic expansion. However, NET-Fuels reduces directly and indirectly total climate change impacts relative to a scenario noNF: approximately -1.60 MtCO₂eq in 2030 and -24.4 MtCO₂eq in 2050. Under a linear scale-up assumption from 27 plants (2030) to 500 plants (2050), avoided emissions are estimated at ~ 260 MtCO₂eq cumulatively over the period, excluding the carbon removal activities which are here modelled to produce tradable carbon credits and thus not accounted for as emission reduction.

The effect of NET-Fuels deployment across the 2030 and 2050 scenarios also show a decrease in material and resource exploitation compared to the same time horizon following the system demand trend projection without the technology penetration in the global system. Employment impacts derived from labour satellite accounts, on the other hand, show that while total employment rises compared to 2020 in baseline growth scenarios, a small but systematic contraction is induced by NET-Fuels deployment.

Across 2030–2050, NET-Fuels deployment produces a measurable structural decarbonisation effect, shifting production from fossil supply chains toward NF products and co-products, and delivering net GHG reductions relative to a baseline counterfactual. Material and resource benefits are directionally positive but modest,

while employment effects are slightly negative at the system level due to the contraction of labour fossil-linked activities and broader productivity dynamics.

The Deliverable is accompanied by a simplified Excel-based calculator that reproduces the main logic of the input-output impact calculations.

1. Introduction and Task 4.4 scope

Deliverable D4.4 presents the methodological framework and quantitative assessment results developed under Task 4.4 “Studying NET-Fuels impact in the society” of Work Package 4 (Sustainability and carbon sink assessment). The task investigates the economy-wide effects associated with the deployment and scale-up of NET-Fuels technology by means of an environmentally extended input-output modelling approach based on the EXIOBASE3 database.

The assessment focuses on linking the NET-Fuels product system to corresponding products, supply chains, economic sectors and end uses, and on quantifying the induced economic, employment, emission, and resource effects across sectors and geographic regions. The modelling framework enables the estimation of both direct and indirect spill-over effects associated with the introduction and expansion of NET-Fuels production under defined feedstock availability constraints.

According to the Description of Action (DoA), Task 4.4 is designed as analytical activities aimed at quantifying the economy-wide implications of introducing and scaling up the NET-Fuels technology. The task begins with the systematic integration of the NET-Fuels product system within a comprehensive macroeconomic modelling framework. In practical terms, this requires the explicit connection of NET-Fuels products and processes to the corresponding supply products and economic sectors represented in the EXIOBASE3 database. Each relevant input and output of the NET-Fuels value chain (including feedstocks, intermediate products, final fuels, and co-products) is mapped to existing product and industry categories (for example, residual biomass streams linked to agriculture and forestry activities, and produced fuels linked to refined fuel products and energy supply sectors). This mapping step creates a connection between the technology-specific process data, generated within the project, and the economic-industrial structure used for impact assessment.

Once the product and sector mapping is established, regional and sectoral data are aggregated in line with the classification and aggregation rules defined in earlier project activities (notably Task 4.1) and aligning with EXIOBASE sectoral categorization. The original high-resolution structure of EXIOBASE3, which distinguishes hundreds of products, industries, emission types, and resource categories across multiple regions is consolidated into project-relevant sector groups following international industrial classification standards (ISIC-based aggregation). This aggregation step allows the results to be interpreted more clearly by stakeholders and policy makers.

A further element of Task 4.4 is the definition of realistic limits to the potential expansion of the NET-Fuels industry. Rather than assuming unconstrained growth, the modelling framework introduces explicit boundary conditions based on the maximum availability of treatable residual and waste biomass. While NET-Fuels scale-up based on biomass availability still presents significant assumptions, these limits represent an important upper technical potential for technology deployment. Biomass availability data are derived from project partner data and assessments. By using this maximum feedstock availability as a limiting factor, the analysis defines expansion scenarios and calculates corresponding [minimum and maximum] levels of industry scale-up.

Within these defined expansion boundaries, the model was developed on Python to compute and interpret the economic effects associated with NET-Fuels deployment. Using the environmentally extended input-output framework, changes in final demand and sectoral economic exchanges linked to NET-Fuels production are propagated through inter-industry supply chains. This allows for the estimation of direct, indirect, and induced effects on total output. The results are expressed in monetary terms and broken down by sector and region, highlighting which parts of the economy mainly experience increases or decreases in activity as a consequence of the technology introduction.

Building on the same modelling structure, Task 4.4 also quantifies the associated labour, emission, and resource-use effects by means of EXIOBASE3 satellite accounts. These extensions link each sector's economic activity to employment by skill level and gender, multiple emission categories, and detailed material and resource extraction indicators. By combining the economic propagation results with these satellite accounts, the analysis estimates spill-over effects on employment generation, environmental pressures, and resource demand across sectors and geographic areas. This integrated perspective supports a comprehensive assessment of the societal implications of NET-Fuels deployment, taking into account sustainability assessment objectives of WP4.

The Deliverable provides both the methodological description and the quantitative modelling results. In addition, a simplified calculation tool (Excel-based calculator) is developed to support transparency, reproducibility, and usability of results by stakeholders and policy makers.

Task 4.4 is led by UNIBO, with contributions from SUT, ITHAKA, REACH, WRG, and FRA, particularly in relation to feedstock availability data, sector classification, and interpretation of results.

2. System Definition, Boundaries, Scenarios and Time Horizon

The modelling framework adopted in Task 4.4 builds upon Deliverable D4.1, where the overall sustainability assessment architecture of the NET-Fuels project was defined, including product system description, functional units, scenario structure, and system definition. The present assessment approaches the assessment within a macro-economic, input-output context.

The NET-Fuels system considered in this deliverable represents an integrated biomass conversion pathway in which residual and waste-based feedstocks are transformed through combined thermochemical and bio-electrochemical processes into renewable fuels and co-products. As already structured in D4.1, the exploitation pathways include multiple output streams — such as renewable gaseous and liquid fuels, hydrogen-rich fractions, and carbonaceous co-products — each associated with distinct downstream uses and substitution effects in existing markets. These exploitation pathways form the basis for linking NET-Fuels outputs to corresponding product groups and user sectors in the economy-wide database, enabling the modelling of substitution and spill-over effects across supply chains rather than limiting the analysis to a single-product perspective

The definition of system boundaries follows the product-system logic established in D4.1 and extends it to an economy-wide perspective. The core boundary includes all stages from residual biomass collection and pre-treatment to conversion, upgrading, distribution, and final fuel use. In Task 4.4 this technology-centered boundary is embedded within a broader socio-economic system boundary through the input-output framework, allowing upstream and downstream interdependencies to be captured across all connected sectors. In line with the D4.1 methodological choices, the boundaries are primarily product-oriented, while remaining compatible with process-oriented representations when required by specific feedstock or technology configurations. Furthermore, the boundary definition explicitly acknowledges the social acceptance dimension introduced in D4.1, where stakeholder perception, adoption conditions, and societal response are recognised as influencing the realistic deployment level of the technology. While social acceptance is not modelled quantitatively in the input-output calculations, it is reflected qualitatively in the scenario interpretation and in the definition of conservative versus high-uptake deployment cases

The functional unit logic applied in the modelling is aligned with the dual framing introduced in D4.1, where both process-oriented and product-oriented functional units were defined. Product-oriented functional units relate impacts to the amount of energy carrier produced (e.g., energy content of renewable fuel output), enabling comparison with fossil and renewable reference fuels. Process-oriented functional units relate instead to the treatment of a given quantity of feedstock (e.g., mass or volume of residual biomass processed), supporting consistent evaluation across alternative feedstock streams. In Task 4.4, these functional unit definitions are translated into input-output demand shocks and scaling factors, ensuring that economy-wide effects remain coherent with the micro-level functional references defined earlier in the project

Overall, Deliverable D4.4 does not redefine the NET-Fuels system, boundaries, or scenarios, but explicitly operationalises and quantifies them aligning to the previous deliverables in WP4. In this way, the work is built on previous assumptions and results while extending its framework from methodological definition to quantitative socio-economic, environmental, and resource impact estimation.

3. 3. Methodological Framework

3.1 Conceptual approach to socio-economic assessment

The conceptual basis of the assessment follows a prospective and consequential approach, with an innovative sustainability assessment practice for emerging energy technologies. Rather than attributing impacts only to the foreground technology system, the framework evaluates how the introduction and scale-up of NET-Fuels modifies production structures, inter-industry exchanges, and environmental pressures across the wider economy. This perspective is aligned with hybrid and consequential modelling approaches described in the recent literature on prospective sustainability assessment of bioenergy and waste-based technologies, where input-output (IO) modelling is coupled with life cycle thinking and scenario-based expansion logic. The NET-Fuels technology is therefore represented not as an isolated production unit but as a new or expanded set of product flows embedded within the economic system. Its inputs (residual biomass, utilities, auxiliary materials) and outputs (renewable fuels and co-products) are connected to existing product groups and sectors in the economic database.

The modelling architecture integrates three complementary methodological components:

Table 1. Modelling architecture

Environmentally extended input-output (EE-IO) modelling for economy-wide propagation of demand and production shock
Hybrid IO–LCA logic for linking technology-specific product systems to macro-sectoral representations
Prospective scenario modelling of technology expansion under feedstock and capacity constraints

Such structure integrates different sustainability assessment methodologies aspects defined, connecting process-level technology analysis and macro socio-economic impact assessment.

3.2 Input-Output and Environmentally Extended IO basis

The modelling approach adopted in this assessment combines a technology-specific foreground description with an economy-wide input-output (IO) representation of the background system. The first step consists in the explicit characterization of the NET-Fuels technology in terms of its physical and functional input and output flows. This foreground system description provides the basis for the subsequent hybrid integration with the macro-economic IO framework. At the foreground level, all exchanges are classified into elementary flows and intermediate flows. Elementary flows represent exchanges between the technosphere and the natural environment. These include resource extractions entering the economic system without previous transformation (such as residual biomass, water, or primary energy carriers) and emissions released to environmental compartments without further economic processing. Intermediate flows instead represent exchanges occurring entirely within the technosphere, that is, goods, materials, and energy carriers supplied by one economic activity and used by another. Examples include electricity, auxiliary materials, process chemicals, and logistics services used by NET-Fuels plants.

Within the intermediate flows, a specific subset is identified as functional flows, namely flows that provide a defined economic function and may substitute existing market products. Typical examples include renewable fuels produced by NET-Fuels that substitute fossil fuels, or recovered co-products that replace conventional materials. These functional flows are central in the consequential interpretation of results, as they define substitution relationships within the economy.

In a conventional process-based LCA, intermediate flows would be linked to background datasets through process libraries. In the present framework, intermediate flows are converted into monetary equivalents and embedded into an IO table of interlinked economic sectors. This enables the integration of the foreground

technology into the full system of economic supply and use relationships and allows economy-wide propagation of effects.

Formally, the IO system at time step t is described by the standard demand-driven Leontief model.

Being:

- x_t = gross output vector (sectoral total production)
- Z_t = intermediate transaction matrix
- A_t = technical coefficient matrix
- y_t = final demand vector
- i = summation vector (vector of ones)
- t = time

The relationship between intermediate transactions and output is:

$$Z_t = A_t \cdot x_t$$

(Eq. 1)

Where x_t is the output vector of the economic system.

Technical coefficients are defined as:

$$a_{ij,t} = \frac{Z_{ij,t}}{x_{j,t}}$$

(Eq. 2)

Where $a_{ij,t}$ represents the monetary input from sector i required per monetary unit of output of sector j at time t .

The sectoral output balance equation is:

$$x_t = Z_t i + y_t$$

(Eq. 3)

Substituting Eq. (1) into Eq. (3) gives:

$$x_t = A_t x_t + y_t$$

(Eq. 4)

which leads to the Leontief solution:

$$x_t = (I - A)^{-1} y_t$$

(Eq. 5)

where I is the identity matrix and $(I - A)^{-1}$ is the Leontief inverse, representing total (direct and indirect) production requirements per unit of final demand.

The integration of NET-Fuels into the IO system is implemented through matrix augmentation, a standard hybrid IO–LCA technique. In this approach, additional rows and columns are introduced (or existing ones are modified) to represent the new technology activities and their product flows within the system structure.

$$A_t^* = A_t + \Delta A_t$$

(Eq. 6)

where ΔA_t represents the technology-induced modifications reflecting NET-Fuels inputs, outputs, and substitutions at time t . This formulation allows scenario-based expansion of the technology while preserving the base IO accounting structure.

Environmental and resource impacts are computed using environmentally extended IO formulation. Let:

- B = environmental stressor matrix (extensions per unit output), containing coefficients of emissions or resource use per unit of sector output
- C = characterization matrix, converting stressors into impact category indicators

h_t = impact indicator vector at time t

Total impacts are calculated as:

$$h_t = CBx_t$$

(Eq. 7)

Matrix B includes sector-specific extension coefficients (e.g., kg CO₂ per monetary unit of output, number of employees per monetary unit), while matrix C contains characterization factors mapping extensions to impact categories (e.g., GHG to climate change indicators, pollutant emissions to acidification or eutrophication potentials). In the present implementation, extension and characterization coefficients are treated as time-invariant, although the framework allows future introduction of time-dependent coefficients. Only GHG were selected as climate indicators.

Scenario results are evaluated by comparing two system states: a reference configuration without NET-Fuels deployment and 2030/2050 deployment scenarios including technology expansion. The net consequence attributable to the technology is computed as the difference between scenario and reference impact vectors:

$$\Delta h_t = h_t^{NET-Fuels} - h_t^{reference}$$

(Eq. 8)

This differential formulation allows for a consequential interpretation of results and quantifies the broader economic environmental and social effects associated with technology implementation over the considered time horizon.

This modelling structure enables the estimation of indirect supply-chain effects that are not captured in process-based inventories alone. When a new technology increases demand for certain inputs or substitutes existing products, IO modelling captures how these changes propagate through all upstream production layers.

By multiplying the Leontief inverse with extension coefficients, it becomes possible to compute total (direct plus indirect) environmental and socio-economic effects associated with changes in final demand, intermediate demand or sectoral output. This framework applies the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) principles and is widely used for consumption-based and technology-consequential footprint calculations (Stadler et al., 2018).

In Task 4.4, IO modelling is used in a consequential shock mode. NET-Fuels deployment is represented as an exogenous change in demand and supply structure, implemented through technology-linked product flows mapped to IO sectors, and the resulting changes in output, value added, and extensions are computed through the Leontief framework.

3.3 Hybrid IO–LCA perspective

To represent NET-Fuels within the IO framework, a hybrid IO–LCA logic is applied. Hybridization combines the detailed technological representation typical of process-based LCA with IO modelling. This approach is here used for emerging technologies whose foreground processes are known in detail but whose economy-wide interactions are not yet existing and must be assessed at aggregated sector level (Porcelli et al, 2023). The hybrid structure implemented in Task 4.4 follows a coupling logic, in which technology-specific data are first developed outside the IO model and then integrated through mapping and scaling procedures. Technology foreground data, including feedstock inputs, conversion yields, product outputs, and co-product distributions are translated into equivalent product flows and linked to corresponding IO product and industry categories. This approach put together strategies described for consequential and prospective hybrid models in the literature. Through mapping, the NET-Fuels product system becomes a sub-system of the IO structure. Its scale is controlled by scenario parameters (plant numbers, output volumes, feedstock availability), and its effects are propagated through the Leontief model.

3.4 Prospective system expansion

The prospective and dynamic logic adopted in Task 4.4 is directly informed by the modelling framework proposed by Porcelli et al., where environmentally extended IO analysis is combined with scenario-based technology diffusion modelling to evaluate emerging bioenergy technologies at continental scale.

In that framework, technology deployment is represented as a time-dependent expansion of production capacity, expressed for example through the number of operating plants and their output levels at future milestone years. The IO system is then “shocked” by introducing additional demand and substitution flows associated with the new technology, and results are compared against a counterfactual baseline without technology adoption.

Task 4.4 adopts the same core principles, adapted to the NET-Fuels context and to the DoA requirements: technology expansion is modelled through bounded scenarios defined by minimum and maximum deployment levels; expansion limits are constrained by feedstock availability rather than unconstrained market growth; a counterfactual reference system without NET-Fuels deployment is defined for comparison; results are expressed as differential impacts between deployment and reference cases.

Unlike fully dynamic integrated assessment models, the IO coefficient structure is held constant (as specified in the DoA), and the prospective dimension is implemented through scenario scaling rather than endogenous structural change. This corresponds to a scenario-driven, low-level coupling approach, where future technology penetration is externally defined and imposed on the IO system.

Sensitivity drivers, such as substitution ratios, yields, and feedstock bounds, are treated parametrically and reported as scenario ranges rather than precise forecasts, in line with recommendations from prospective IO-LCA literature.

3.5 NET-Fuels Penetration Modelling through Matrix Augmentation

The integration of NET-Fuels technology into the economy-wide input-output framework is implemented through a matrix augmentation procedure. This approach allows the explicit introduction of new technology-derived products and functional flows into the input-output tables. The method follows the hybrid IO augmentation logic described in the prospective IO-LCA literature and applied in dynamic technology assessment frameworks.

In practical terms, the original input-output system is expanded by introducing additional product and sector entries representing NET-Fuels functional outputs. Each new functional flow is represented through the addition of one row and one column to the transaction matrix and corresponding technical coefficient matrix. The augmentation is applied to the region(s) where technology deployment is assumed to occur — in this study, limited to the European region — while the rest of the world structure remains unchanged except for trade-linked effects.

Let the original technical coefficient matrix at time t be:

$$A_t \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$$

After augmentation with k NET-Fuels functional products, the matrix becomes:

$$A_t * \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+k) \times (n+k)}$$

Analogous augmentation is applied to the intermediate transaction matrix and the final demand vector .

3.5.1 Substitution factors

The coefficients in the newly introduced rows — representing the distribution of new NET-Fuels products across using sectors — are defined using substitution factors. These factors quantify the degree to which a new technology product replaces an existing competing product in the economy.

For a new product substituting an existing product , the substitution factor at time t is defined as:

$$sf_{s,n}(t) = \frac{x_n(t)}{x_s(t)}$$

(Eq. 8)

where:

- x_n = total output of the new NET-Fuels product at time t (scenario-defined target value)
- x_s = total output of the substituted conventional product at time t (model-calculated value)

This ratio expresses the market share of the new product relative to the conventional one under the scenario assumptions.

3.5.2 Modification of technical coefficients – rows (product substitution)

Substitution factors are used to modify the technical coefficients in the rows corresponding to the substituted and substituting products. Let be the original coefficient describing the input of product s required by sector j . Under substitution, this coefficient is split between the original product s and the new product n .

The new coefficients become:

$$a_{nj}(t) = a_{sj} \cdot sf_{s,n}(t)$$

(Eq. 9)

$$a_{sj}(t) = a_{sj} \cdot (1 - sf_{s,n}(t))$$

(Eq. 10)

Thus, the input previously supplied entirely by product s is partially reallocated to product n according to the substitution factor. Under the assumption of perfect functional substitution, the sum of coefficients remains constant:

$$a_{nj}(t) + a_{sj}(t) = a_{sj}$$

(Eq. 11)

3.5.3 Modification of final demand – substitution in use

The same substitution logic is applied to the final demand vector. Let be the original final demand for the substituted product. The demand is reallocated between the new and old products as follows:

$$y_n(t) = y_s \cdot sf_{s,n}(t)$$

(Eq. 11)

$$y_s(t) = y_s \cdot (1 - sf_{s,n}(t))$$

(Eq. 12)

This ensures that substitution affects not only intermediate consumption but also final uses (e.g., fuel consumption by households or transport sectors), therefore taking into account the assumed market penetration of NET-Fuels products. Substitution relationships are defined product-by-product based on functional equivalence assumptions established in the technology mapping phase (e.g., renewable fuel fractions substituting fossil fuels, recovered nutrient products substituting mineral fertilizers, technology electricity output substituting grid electricity from selected generation mixes).

3.5.4 Regional substitution scope

Substitution is applied primarily within the region of technology deployment. NET-Fuels energy products are assumed to be consumed mainly within the European market; therefore, substitution is implemented for corresponding European product rows and final demand elements. For selected co-products with internationally traded markets, substitution may extend partially to external regions once defined market share thresholds are exceeded. This treatment allows regionally differentiated substitution patterns while maintaining global accounting balance.

3.5.5 Definition of new columns – technology input structure

While new rows describe how the new products are used across sectors, the new columns describe how the NET-Fuels sectors purchase inputs from the rest of the economy. Coefficients in the new columns are derived from the monetary structure of the technology foreground system.

Let:

- z_{in} = monetary value of input from sector i required by NET-Fuels product sector n
- R_n = total monetary revenue of NET-Fuels product n

Input coefficients are defined as:

$$a_{in} = \frac{z_{in}}{R_n}$$

(Eq. 13)

These coefficients are calculated from technology cost and revenue structure and allocated across input sectors according to their economic weight in total production cost. In accordance with the modelling assumptions defined in the DoA, prices are treated as constant over time. Therefore, once defined, these input coefficients remain time-invariant.

This implies that technology input recipes are assumed stable across the scenario time horizon, while total output levels scale with scenario deployment targets.

3.5.6 Time-dependent augmented system

At each scenario time step t , the augmented coefficient matrix incorporates substitution-adjusted coefficients. This time-indexed augmented system enables scenario-dependent recalculation of total outputs and, through environmental and socio-economic extensions, of the associated impact indicators.

Scenario results are finally evaluated relative to a non-deployment reference system, and the difference is interpreted as the net consequence of NET-Fuels technology introduction over the considered time horizon.

3.5.7 Final demand projection

The baseline input-output tables adopted in this assessment are derived from EXIOBASE3 and refer to a historical reference year. In their original configuration, these tables describe the inter-sectoral production structure and final demand composition of the economy at that time and are therefore not directly suitable for representing future economic conditions. In order to support prospective scenario analysis, the input-output system is updated to reflect expected developments in sectoral demand and selected structural characteristics.

Scenarios are implemented by modifying two main elements of the model: the final demand vector and selected technical coefficients associated with electricity production sectors. This scenario-update procedure follows established prospective input-output modelling practice, in which future system states are approximated by structured adjustments to demand patterns and key sector coefficients rather than by full macroeconomic re-forecasting. For all sectors except electricity production, future final demand is projected on the basis of historical trends available in the EXIOBASE time series. Sector-specific final demand values

over the historical period are used to estimate a linear trend through regression. For each sector i , final demand is represented as a function of time according to:

$$y_i(t) = \alpha_i + \beta_i t$$

where the parameters represent the sector-specific intercept and time trend estimated from historical observations. Projected future demand for a scenario year is then obtained as:

$$\hat{y}_i(t^*) = \alpha_i + \beta_i t^*$$

The resulting projected values are used to update the non-electricity components of the final demand vector in each future scenario year. Electricity production sectors are treated separately because they are expected to undergo significant structural transformation driven by energy transition and climate policy. Instead of extrapolating past trends, their future structure is aligned with externally defined energy scenario pathways. In practice, the input structures of electricity generation sectors are adjusted to reflect changes in the technology mix of power production over time. The relative contributions of different generation technologies (such as fossil, renewable, and other sources) are updated according to recognized long-term energy outlook scenarios, aggregated to match the regional and sectoral resolution of the model.

Linear trend extrapolation may produce negative final demand values in long-term projections. Since negative consumption is not economically meaningful for the sectors considered, projected final demand was bounded at zero to satisfy IO modelling assumptions.

3.5.8 EXIOBASE3 structure and relevance

EXIOBASE3 provides a time series of harmonized supply-use and IO tables with high sectoral and environmental detail. It is particularly suitable for the objectives of Task 4.4 for several reasons. It offers high sectoral resolution, with supply-use tables structured around approximately 200 products and 163 industries for Eu countries and extra-EU ones. This level of disaggregation is especially important for representing environmentally relevant sectors such as agriculture, energy production, resource extraction, and waste treatment, which are directly connected to NET-Fuels inputs and outputs. The supply-use structure preserves product detail even when industries produce multiple outputs.

Moreover, EXIOBASE3 includes a set set of environmental and socio-economic satellite accounts, compiled across countries and sectors. The selected ones for this assessment are:

- I. air emission accounts covering greenhouse gases and air pollutants;
- II. material flow accounts with detailed biomass, mineral, and fossil resource categories;
- III. water use accounts;
- IV. labour accounts disaggregated by skill level and gender.

EXIOBASE3 incorporates methodological elements from physical and hybrid supply-use and waste accounting, including residues treatment sectors and material flow checks. Its waste and material extensions are aligned with hybrid and waste IO approaches, where waste is treated as “material for treatment” and recycling and recovery are modelled as transformation activities rather than simple disposals.

The database has been widely used in environmental footprint and policy analysis contexts and is explicitly designed to support sustainability and resource-efficiency assessments at EU and global scale. Its compatibility with environmental-economic accounting standards and its detailed sector classification facilitate aggregation to ISIC-aligned sector groups, as required by Task 4.4 aggregation rules.

4. Feedstock Availability and Expansion Constraints

Biomass categories considered

The list of treatable biomass categories considered in this Task is consistent with the types defined in WP2:

- a. Digestate - an example for residues from agriculture and livestock farming, Digestate obtained from the anaerobic digestion of manure and maize silage;
- b. Prunings - an example for residues from forestry and wood biomass, Offcuts from vineyards and orchards seasonally accumulating in large quantities.
- c. Calamity wood - an example for residues from forestry and wood biomass, Wood that is not suitable for the initially intended material use, coming from damages caused by bark beetle infestation, forest fires and hurricanes or storms;

These groups are variants of feedstocks for the complex NET-Fuels technology chain and became a material input for the Life Cycle Inventory in WP4. Details of the biomass categories considered are described in the report D2.1 - Report on feedstock characterization. This report covered WP2's specific objective O2.1 to test different biogenic residues as feedstock for production of CO₂-negative fuels. It shall be mentioned that D2.1 presents also low lignin biomass (Olive pressing residue, olive stones and hops offcuts) as a potential example for residues from agriculture. It was, however, excluded from further considerations in balancing the process by means of Life Cycle Inventory and will not be analyzed here to maintain consistency.

LCI data integration

For potential industrial scalability, it is essential to declare the baseline of amounts of material and energy consumption required for specific production. Life Cycle Inventory provides a summary of Inputs and Outputs to the NET-Fuels technology chain. Below, a summary of LCI assuming 1 hour of all NET-Fuels modules cooperation at 20 kg/h pellets intake.

Table 2 NET-Fuels Life Cycle Inventory integrated for potential industrial scale-up, 1h operation, INPUTS

Feedstock	INPUTS				
	Pellets, kg	Electricity, kWh	Heat, MJ	Petrol, kg	Water, kg
<i>Digestate</i>	20	115.10	110.88	0	13.52
<i>Wine prunings</i>	20	154.32	0.00	0.52	17.82
<i>Wood</i>	20	126.08	0.00	0.77	13.78

Table 3 NET-Fuels Life Cycle Inventory integrated for potential industrial scale-up, 1h operation, OUTPUTS

Feedstock	OUTPUTS					
	CH ₄ , kg	H ₂ , kg	O ₂ , kg	Biochar, kg	TCR-oil, kg	TCR-water, kg
<i>Digestate</i>	3.06	0.15	8.64	7.12	0.90	5.03
<i>Wine prunings</i>	4.22	0.20	9.16	5.51	1.37	5.10
<i>Wood</i>	3.47	0.10	6.85	5.79	1.67	6.52

Upper bound estimation method

4.2.1 Digestate availability in 2030 and 2050

Digestate quantities are directly linked to the volume and composition of feedstocks processed in anaerobic digestion (AD) plants. Therefore, projections of biogas production provide a foundation for estimating future digestate output. The estimation here was based on research presented in [Error! Reference source not found.]. The aim of that research was to provide an estimation of the sustainable biomass potential availability in the European Union and the UK by 2030 and 2050 and to provide an evaluation of the advanced biofuel potential. Three scenarios have been analysed: i) Low biomass mobilisation, ii) improved mobilisation in selected countries due to improvements in cropping and forest management practices and iii) enhanced availability through Research and Innovation (R&I) measures as well as improved mobilisation due to improvements in cropping and forest management practices.

The forecasts present possible availability of dry manure and maize stover – which, according to D2.1, constitute the input to anaerobic digestion plant with digestate becoming our desired residue. The potential amount of digestate residue $m_{Digestate}$ was estimated using following approach

$$m_{Digestate} = m_M - m_{Biogas} \tag{1}$$

$$m_{Biogas} = m_{VS} \cdot \eta_{AD} \tag{2}$$

$$m_{VS} = m_M \cdot VS\% \tag{3}$$

- m_M – mass of dry manure or maize stover, kg
- m_{Biogas} – mass of gas resulting from anaerobic digestion, kg
- m_{VS} – volatile solids mass in the manure or maize stover, kg
- η_{AD} – conversion efficiency of organic matter to biogas, %
- $VS\%$ – volatile solids mass fraction, %

Conversion efficiency of the AD plant and the volatile solids content of the biomass source were assumed following data in Table 4.

Table 4 Anaerobic digestion parameters for manure and maize

	η_{AD}	$VS\%$	Source
Value range for manure and maize stover	50-75%	70-85%	[Error! Reference source not found.,Error! Reference source not found.]
Value adapted for estimation	70%	80%	

Figure 1 and Figure 2 present the potential availability of digestate (from manure and maize stover, respectively) according to forecasts presented in [Error! Reference source not found.] and own calculations. The results are here shown for the Scenario 3: Enhanced availability through R&I & improved mobilization declared as High variant. This scenario assumes the highest feasible mobilisation of sustainable biomass across all feedstocks in the EU27 and the United Kingdom, enabled by major improvements in agricultural and forestry management practices. It brings roughly 75% of unused, abandoned, and degraded land into biomass production and benefits from research and innovation that raise yields, improve equipment efficiency, and enhance climate-resilient crop varieties. Throughout the system, the focus remains on prioritising residues and waste streams for both energy and non-energy biobased uses.

Figure 1 Digestate from manure potential availability in 2030 and 2050 in European countries

Figure 2 Digestate from maize stover potential availability in 2030 and 2050 in European countries

France is a dominant supplier of this kind of biomass residues. Apparently, the availability of digestate from manure will slightly decrease by 2050, while of digestate from maize stover will slightly increase. However, the amount of available manure will be still almost three times higher than of maize.

4.2.2 Prunings availability in 2030 and 2050

The potential availability of pruning was adapted from research presented in [Error! Reference source not found.]. In this work, pruning (or cutting) is derived from fruit trees, vineyards, olives, and nut trees. They are woody residues produced after cutting, mulching, and chipping activities. It is the result of normal pruning management needed to maintain the orchards and improve their productivity.

Figure 3 presents potential availability of prunings for bioenergy in the year 2030 and 2050. It is an estimate for Scenario 2 assuming improved biomass mobilisation in selected EU countries with either high biomass potential or favourable conditions such as strong policies, infrastructure, or low supply costs. It includes enhanced agricultural and forestry practices and brings about 50% of unused, abandoned, and degraded land into biomass production. The scenario continues to prioritise residues and wastes while ensuring that biodiversity is protected through conservation measures and sustainable land management.

Figure 3 Pruning potential availability in 2030 and 2050

According to the forecasts, the year 2050 will provide higher availability of pruning. It is also evident that this kind of biomass residue is available in fewer countries than maize or manure.

4.2.3 Calamity wood availability in 2030 and 2050

These estimates posed the greatest challenge in the task. There are no direct scientific forecasts for European calamity wood volumes in 2030 or 2050. Therefore, the ranges were estimated by combining recent historical baselines with climate-driven disturbance multipliers for three sources of calamity wood: (a) bark beetle infestation, (b) wildfire, and (c) storms.

Historic data for damaged wood is taken from sector reports and literature [Error! Reference source not found., Error! Reference source not found., Error! Reference source not found., Error! Reference source not found.], and the possible increase of availability is based on climate-risk evidence for forest damages by infestations, fire activity, and storms [Error! Reference source not found., Error! Reference source not found.]. Volumes are first estimated in m³/a, then converted to mass using wood-type densities (exemplary density of dry wood is 600 kg/m³, exemplary wood moisture content is 50% [Error! Reference source not found.]). Results are presented as low and high output scenario.

a. Bark beetle.

It was assumed that bark beetle activity will continue under milder winters and drought stress, leading to steady outbreaks of infestation [Error! Reference source not found., Error! Reference source not found.]. For 2030, a modest increase (+5 to 10%) is applied to the historical beetle-damage baseline. For 2050, a scenario following +15% of calamity wood multiplier is used [Error! Reference source not found.].

b. Wildfires

Given the rapidly increasing frequency and burned area in Europe and the broader global outlook [Error! Reference source not found., Error! Reference source not found., Error! Reference source not found.], an increase of calamity wood amounts coming from this disaster is assumed at the level of +15–20% by 2030 and +30% by 2050 to the fire-damage baseline. It should be highlighted that the usability is time-limited: 6–18 months post-fire depending on species. It means that a stricter salvage factor ($\approx 0.4\text{--}0.7$) should be used to account for rapid quality loss and safety/access issues [Error! Reference source not found.]. A salvage factor represents how much of the damaged wood can realistically be recovered and used after a calamity, because of decay, degradation, and accessibility.

c. Storms

A historical storm baseline of 25–35 million m^3/a was adopted with an increase level of +20–30% by 2030 to reflect intensifying events. For 2050, literature supports assumptions of two times frequent events than the baseline [Error! Reference source not found.]. Storm salvage factor is higher than for fires, e.g. 0.7–0.9.

Possible availability of calamity wood coming from these 3 sources, according to Low and High scenarios for 2030 and 2050 is presented in the cumulative chart in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Potential calamity wood availability in 2030 and 2050 following Low and High scenarios

In terms of share, bark beetle infestation is responsible for the greatest part of emerging calamity wood in all cases.

4.2.4 Feedstocks availabilities – results

The estimated amounts of feedstocks availabilities are presented in the following tables.

Table 5 Digestate and Prunings availability in Europe in 2030 and 2050, following three scenarios presented in [Error! Reference source not found.]

	Recalculation 2030, Mt/a			Recalculation 2050, Mt/a		
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Digestate from manure	22.24	26.68	27.77	20.01	24.01	24.99
Digestate from maize stover	8.90	9.69	9.79	9.79	10.65	10.77

Prunings	3.89	6.04	9.82	4.66	7.25	11.79
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Table 6 Calamity wood availability in Europe in 2030 and 2050, following potential low and high calamity scenarios

	2030 (low)	2030 (high)	2050 (low)	2050 (high)
	Mt/a	Mt/a	Mt/a	Mt/a
(a) Bark beetle infestation	54	81	62.1	93.15
(b) Wildfires	22.5	36	29.25	46.8
(c) Storms	29.25	40.95	45	63
Sum	105.75	157.95	136.35	202.95

Industrial expansion boundary conditions

The industrial deployment of a complex Net-Fuels technology chain requires clearly defined technical and environmental boundary conditions. Feedstock quality is one of the main limiting factors: pelletized biomass residues—such as calamity wood, pruning, and digestate solids—must exhibit low contamination, controlled moisture levels, and sufficient energy content to ensure stable conversion. Reliable operation also depends on a secure feedstock supply sourced within a radius of less than 150 km and supported by approximately six months of seasonal storage.

Within the thermo-catalytic reforming (TCR) unit, thermal conversion demands effective gas cleaning to prevent fouling and catalyst degradation in downstream systems. The cleaned syngas is subsequently directed to an oxy-fuel combustion chamber, producing CO₂-rich flue gases forming the feedstock for the bioelectro-methanation (BEM) unit. Methane formation in the BEM reactor requires a stable hydrogen-to-CO₂ ratio, controlled operating temperatures, and moderate pressures to maintain biological performance and ensure methane upgrading.

Across the integrated technology chain, maintaining high levels of heat and energy recovery is essential for system efficiency. All final products must meet strict regulatory thresholds—biomethane with at least 96% CH₄ for grid injection, certified biochar for environmental applications, and stabilized bio-oil for safe handling and utilization. System must allow for permit-compliant emissions, and the proper treatment of wastewater. Finally, adequate infrastructure—such as grid access points, hydrogen handling systems, and CO₂ recycling or capture capacity—is a critical boundary for enabling scalable, reliable, and sustainable industrial operation.

5. NET-Fuels System and Mapping to EXIOBASE3

NET-Fuels I/O system definition and foreground

The analysis of the foreground system involved data collection and calculation procedures built on T4.2 to quantify relevant inputs and outputs of the specific TCR-PSA-Oxyfuel-BEM combined technology. A schematic representation of the processes included in the system and the main flows among them is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5. NET-Fuels process flow diagram

Table 7 lists inputs and outputs by each unit process considered in the model for the foreground system.

Table 7. NET-Fuels process units, input and output flows

Process units and main input and output flows identified for the foreground system			
Process	Flow	I/O	u.m.
Dewatering, drying and pelletizing	Digestate (from maize and manure – water content 90%)	I	kg
	Pruning (water content 7.9%)	I	kg
	Calamity wood (water content 7.6%)	I	kg
	Thermal energy	I	MJ
	Electricity	I	kWh
	Petrol	O	kg
	Dry Feedstock	O	kg
	Water	O	kg
TCR	Digestate	I	kg
	Pruning	I	kg
	Wood	I	kg
	Electricity	I	kWh
	Thermal energy	I	MJ

	Oil	0	kg
	Bio-oil	0	kg
	Biochar	0	kg
	Syngas	0	kg
	Carbon Credits (from biochar)	0	kg
PSA	Syngas	1	kg
	Electricity	1	kWh
	Hydrogen	0	kg
Oxyfuel combustion	De-hydrogenized syngas	1	kg
	Oxygen	1	kg
	Flue gas (Carbon Dioxide)	0	kg
	Heat	0	MJ
BEM	Electricity	1	kWh
	Flue gas (Carbon Dioxide)	1	kg
	Water	1	kg
	Syn-methane	0	kg
	Oxygen	0	kg

Figure 6. NET-Fuels process units and main input and output flows

The objective of this assessment is to represent a realistic yet ambitious scale-up trajectory towards commercial penetration of NET-fuels across Europe by 2030 and 2050, modelled by feedstock availability constraints and industrial deployment feasibility. Unlike single-feedstock systems, the NET-Fuels configuration assessed here relies on three heterogeneous residual biomass streams: digestate from maize and manure, agricultural pruning residues, and calamity wood (disturbance-induced forest biomass).

The feedstock amount virtually processed is defined using an upper boundary availability calculation (Chapter 4) derived from three biomass supply scenarios. To ensure conservative modelling assumptions and avoid over-estimation of technical potential, the intermediate scenario was selected. Furthermore, only one third of the available biomass under that scenario is assumed to be mobilised for NET-Fuels production. Such assumption relies on different aspects like the competing uses of biomass (soil amendment, animal bedding, material uses, alternative bioenergy pathways), together with logistical and spatial constraints, and realistic mobilisation rates observed in biomass markets.

Under this conservative mobilisation factor, available biomass amounts by 2030 to around 58 Mt/year across the three feedstocks and 11.56 Mt digestate, 2.41 Mt pruning, 56.22 Mt of calamity wood by 2050. These volumes define a minimum and a maximum scenario of NET-Fuels technology penetration. Although the 2030 58 Mt/y of biomass would theoretically allow for rapid expansion, early-stage diffusion constraints are assumed to preserve the supply-chain maturation process. 27 commercial plants are assumed to be deployed by 2030 and 500 by 2050, with a capacity of 20t/h.

Table 8. NET-Fuels plant scale-up targets for 2030 and 2050

NET-Fuels Target		
Year	n. of plants	Production capacity
2030	27	20t/h
2050	500	20t/h

A representative generic NET-Fuels plant model is considered to define the foreground system. Mean yields were calculated across feedstock types to derive a harmonised input-output structure suitable for integration into the IO framework. Mean product distributions were calculated per tonne of dry biomass processed, and these flows were monetised.

In the monetary representation of the foreground system, outputs associated with NET-Fuels functional products (e.g., syn-methane, bio-oil, biochar, oxygen and carbon credits) are treated as revenues, whereas feedstock inputs, electricity, auxiliary materials and process services are treated as NET-Fuels consumptions and thus expenditures. To distinguish NET-Fuels outputs from existing market products in the input–output system, newly introduced products were labelled with the prefix “NF_” (e.g., *NF_Methane*, *NF_Biooil*, *NF_Biochar*, *NF_Oxygen*, *NF_CarbonCredits*).

Prices for NET-Fuels products and inputs were collected directly from project partners and are aligned, where possible, with the preliminary techno-economic assessment of the technology. However, when integrating the foreground system into the EXIOBASE monetary IO structure, an important adjustment was required. EXIOBASE operates in monetary units (M€) and represents sectoral outputs at average market prices. For example, in the case of renewable synthetic methane, the unit production cost (and therefore selling price) derived from techno-economic assessment is significantly higher than the average economic value of conventional natural gas represented in EXIOBASE. If the full NET-Fuels techno-economic price of synthetic methane were directly used for substitution in the IO table, the monetary weight of the *NF_Methane* sector would become disproportionately large relative to the natural gas sector. The higher unit price of synthetic methane would artificially amplify its market share in monetary terms, even if physical substitution volumes remain realistic. The same happens for biochar when compared to other soil amendment methods. To avoid this distortion, a price normalisation approach was adopted for substitution modelling.

Table 9. Monetary inputs and outputs considered in the assessment

Inputs and Outputs monetary flows (1 plant, 20t/h capacity)			
Inputs	MEur	Outputs	Eur
Feedstock	0.5	NF_Biochar	4.8
Electricity	5	NF_Methane	10.5
Petrol	0.9	NF_Bio-oil	3.15
Thermal energy	2	NF_Hydrogen	0.15
Concrete	0.01	NF_Oxygen	7
Steel	0.09	NF_Carbon Credits	6.9
Transport	0.003	Wastewater treatment	0.3

In addition to the main NET-Fuels I/O flows, the use of average materials used for the building of a commercial plant was assumed: specific data were not available, thus data of similar plants type were approximated, allocating the flows over the operational lifetime of the plant (20 years) to simplify the assessment.

Product mapping procedure

The mapping procedure consisted in linking physical input and output flow of the foreground system to the most equivalent EXIOBASE product category. Each NF flow is linked to the IO category that would otherwise provide the same economic function in the absence of technology deployment. Where necessary, split allocations were introduced to reflect realistic inputs and outputs allocation. EXIOBASE sectors were then linked to the International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (ISIC) (Rev. 5).

Table 10. NET-Fuels mapping to EXIOBASE and ISIC sectors, plus relative substitution efficiency when less than 100%

	EXIOBASE	ISIC Code	ISIC Sectors
Pruning	Crops nec (not elsewhere classified)	A0161	Support activities for crop production

Calamity wood	Wood waste for treatment: incineration (50%)	E3821	Materials recovery
	Wood waste for treatment: landfill (50%)	E3812	Treatment and disposal of non-hazardous waste
Digestate	Manure (biogas treatment) (50%)	A0143	Production of raw milk
	Crops nec (50%)	A0161	Support activities for crop production
Petrol	Gas/Diesel Oil	C1920	Manufacture of refined petroleum products
Thermal energy	Electricity nec	D3510	Electric power generation
Electricity	Electricity nec	D3510	Electric power generation
Concrete	Cement, lime and plaster	C2351	Manufacture of cement
Steel	Basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys and first products thereof	C2410	Manufacture of basic iron and steel
Transport	Other land transportation services	H4920	Freight land transport
Biochar	Chemical and fertilizer minerals, salt and other mining and quarrying products (20%)	B0899	Mining support services
Syn-Methane	Natural gas and services related to natural gas extraction, excluding surveying	B0620	Extraction of natural gas
Hydrogen	Chemicals nec	C2013	Manufacture of basic inorganic chemicals
Oxygen	Chemicals nec (70%)	C2013	Manufacture of basic inorganic chemicals
Carbon credits	Financial intermediation services, except insurance and pension funding services (65)	K6499	Financial intermediation not elsewhere classified
Bio-oil	Heavy Fuel Oil (80%)	C1920	Manufacture of petroleum products
Wastewater	Other waste for treatment: wastewater treatment	E3700	Sewerage

Moreover, some NET-Fuels products cannot have a complete substitution efficiency with existing sectors: biochar can partially alleviate the use of chemical fertilizers, while oxygen produced by the BEM contains

other compounds that could impact on the substitution efficiency with industrial chemicals. In the same way, bio-oil needs to be refined to be considered a bio-diesel usable instead of heavy fuel oils.

The integration of carbon credits generated by biochar application posed a structural modelling challenge within the EXIOBASE IO system. Environmentally extended input–output tables represent established economic sectors and product flows that are within national accounts. The creation of an entirely new “carbon removal market” sector would require rebalancing the system structure, redefining transaction matrices, and introducing additional accounting identities that are not supported by the database. Such a process could be a future development of this assessment method.

Because of such challenges and reasons, carbon credits were mapped to the category “*Financial intermediation services, except insurance and pension funding services*”. Carbon credits can be considered as tradable financial instruments. The financial intermediation sector already includes activities related to monetary asset exchanges, brokerage, and transaction services, making it the closest existing sector proxy for voluntary or compliance carbon markets.

All the products generated by NET-Fuels are expected to be sold within the European Union, for this reason the substitution involves only EU products. It was assumed that, since the virtual plants are located in EU, the intermediate flows are all produced or managed in the same region. Therefore, also the economic effects results isolate EU regions. On the other hand, effects of NET-Fuels technology in terms of environmental and social effects are determined on a global level.

5.1.1 Baseline

The analysis compares the penetration of NET-Fuels under alternative future scenarios against two distinct reference systems. The baseline represents the observed economic structure and final demand configuration in the base year (2020), prior to the introduction of NET-Fuels and before structural transition effects unfold. The differences between NF and noNF scenarios include both NET-Fuels effects and also independent ones such as economic growth, energy transition dynamics. As this comparison would only represent the overall system transformation, it was necessary to isolate NET-Fuels deployment effects, creating same-year counterfactual for noNF scenarios (2030, 2050). The same projections and assumptions are made, but NET-Fuels penetration is set to zero so that the marginal impact is identified.

5.1.2 Energy transition applied to A and y

In the present analysis, the energy transition is embedded directly into the input-output framework by modifying both the matrix of technical coefficients (A) and the final demand vector (y) for electricity-related sectors. The transition trajectory is aligned with a Sustainable Development pathway, reflecting a progressive decarbonisation of the electricity system up to 2050. Data from the “World Energy Outlook” by the International Energy Agency (IEA) (IEA, 2004) were aggregated for EU countries and “Rest of the World” in order to project into the model the future electricity mix outlined by transition scenarios.

Transition factors were defined annually over the period 2011–2050, based on projected changes in the electricity mix. For each electricity technology (e.g. coal, gas, nuclear, wind, photovoltaic, biomass, marine, geothermal), percentage variations relative to the baseline year were specified. These percentage changes were implemented as multiplicative scaling factors applied to the relevant rows of matrix A and to the electricity-related components of vector y.

A reflects inter-sectoral dependencies and its modifications propagate through the economy via supply chains. Reductions in coal coefficients, for example, affect not only the electricity sector but also mining,

transport, refining, and other linked industries. It can be noted how fossil-based technologies (e.g. coal, oil) progressively decrease in relative importance, while renewable technologies (e.g. wind, photovoltaic, biomass, marine) for electricity production increase their contribution.

To maintain the electricity production transition structure also as for the demand side, the same projections were applied to the electricity components of y vector, Thus, both intermediate and final demand changes are captured.

By 2050, the applied changes indicate a pronounced decarbonisation trajectory, particularly in the EU region. In the EU28, fossil-based technologies undergo significant contraction relative to the baseline. Coal-based electricity coefficients decrease by 78.8%, while oil-based electricity declines even more sharply by 92.8%. Gas is reduced by 29.3% and nuclear by 38.5%.

In parallel, renewable electricity technologies exhibit strong expansion. Wind increases by 449.7% and photovoltaic by 427.7%, indicating a major shift toward variable renewables. Solar thermal grows by 1510.4%, while marine energy shows an exceptionally large increase of 9098.7%, reflecting its marginal baseline level and projected future deployment. Biomass increases by 31.8%, geothermal by 52.0%, and hydropower by 23.3%. Overall, these changes point to a substantial reallocation of the electricity production structure away from fossil technologies and towards renewable and emerging low-carbon sources, with particularly strong growth in solar-based and marine technologies.

The transition in the Rest of the World follows a similar but more heterogeneous pattern. Coal decreases by 33.9%, oil by 84.8%, and nuclear by 37.4%, indicating a general contraction of carbon-intensive technologies. However, gas increases by 12.9%, suggesting a transitional role in the decarbonisation pathway. Renewable technologies expand markedly: wind increases by 545.3%, photovoltaic by 8314.9%, and solar thermal by 1108.5%. Biomass grows by 51.5% and geothermal by 139.3%. Compared to the EU28, the RoW trajectory exhibits a stronger late-stage acceleration in photovoltaic deployment, indicating a more pronounced catch-up dynamic in solar technologies.

In the EU28 (YEU), demand-side changes reinforce the structural decarbonisation observed in production. Coal demand decreases by 73.7% and oil by 91.1%, while gas declines by 12.3% and nuclear by 23.8%. At the same time, renewable electricity demand increases substantially. Wind expands by 581.8% and photovoltaic by 554.4%. Solar thermal electricity grows by 1897.1%, marine energy by 11307.6%, biomass by 63.5%, geothermal by 88.6%, and hydropower by 52.9%. These figures confirm that the transition is not confined to intermediate production coefficients but is part of the composition of final electricity demand.

In the Rest of the World (YRW), the demand-side evolution is more uneven. Oil decreases by 59.4%, whereas coal, gas, and nuclear continue to increase moderately, indicating partial persistence of conventional technologies. Nevertheless, renewable technologies display extremely rapid growth, particularly photovoltaics, which increase by 22405%, followed by wind (+1625.7%), solar thermal (+3132.0%), and biomass (+305.1%). This pattern suggests a delayed but highly accelerated renewable deployment trajectory, characterised by a relevant expansion of solar technologies in later stages of the transition.

Figure 7. Technology shares for energy transition pathways in the EU – technical coefficients

Figure 8. Technology shares for energy transition pathways in Rest of the World – technical coefficients

Figure 9. Technology shares for energy transition pathways in the EU - final demand

Figure 10. Technology shares for energy transition pathways in RoW – final demand

6. Results I: Economic Impact Assessment

Sectoral output effects

The introduction of NET-Fuels (NF) technology induces measurable structural adjustments in the production system, as shown by the evolution of sectoral output (x) between 2020, 2030 and 2050. The comparison between the baseline year (2020) and the NF scenarios reveals a progressive reallocation of economic activity across sectors, with effects that intensify over time.

In the modelling framework, the vector of sectoral total outputs was computed for each simulation year starting from the 2020 baseline, calculating both system expansions and contractions with and without the implementation of Net-Fuels technology. The comparative assessment of the NET-Fuels (NF) technology is based on the arithmetic difference between NF and noNF scenarios. This difference isolates the structural “technology-only” effect of NET-Fuels on the economic system, independently of environmental extensions. Change was computed in the geographical area of the EU.

The change in sectoral outputs in the EU-27 region indicates a progressive reallocation of production across sectors, already visible in 2030 and substantially amplified by 2050. In 2030, sectors directly associated with NET-Fuels display positive variations in output, reflecting the initial deployment phase of the technology, corresponding to 27 plants using 140 000t/y of feedstock each. NF_Methane, NF_Biochar, NF_Oxygen and NF_CarbonCredits show measurable increases, although still limited in magnitude compared to 2050, showing a gradual scaling trajectory. In parallel, sectors linked to conventional fossil supply chains begin to exhibit contractions depending on the sectoral shift. “Natural gas extraction and related services”, “Heavy Fuel Oil” and selected energy-intensive industrial activities already show negative variations for the direct substitution with Net-Fuels products, indicating that substitution mechanisms are active but not yet dominant at this stage.

By 2050, the structural transformation becomes considerably more pronounced. The strongest increases in sectoral output are observed for NF_Methane, which expands by $+8.85 \times 10^3$ M€, followed by NF_Biochar by $+4.39 \times 10^3$ M€, NF_Oxygen $+3.78 \times 10^3$ M€, NF_CarbonCredits $+2.55 \times 10^3$ M€ and NF_Biooil $+1.77 \times 10^3$ M€. These increases reflect the endogenous expansion of NET-Fuels production as defined in the scenario design and the progressive substitution of conventional fuels and feedstocks.

Substantial decreases are also observed in “Financial intermediation services” by -6.25×10^3 M€, “Chemical and fertilizer minerals and mining products n.e.c.” by -4.41×10^3 M€, “Chemicals nec” by -4.21×10^3 M€, and the broader “ENERGY” aggregate by -3.25×10^3 M€. “Heavy Fuel Oil” contracts by -1.83×10^3 M€, while “TRANSPORT” shows a reduction of -9.50×10^2 M€. The contraction of fossil extraction and fossil fuel processing activities is directly and indirectly caused by the substitution in the NET-Fuels scenario. The negative variations observed in broader industrial and service aggregates indicate indirect adjustments along the supply chain, rather than isolated sectoral shifts, due to the Leontief inverse application. In economic terms, these indirect effects arise from the intersectoral linkages in the input–output structure of the model: as demand for fossil-based energy carriers and related intermediate inputs declines, upstream sectors supplying goods and services to these activities experience a reduction in output. This includes not only energy-intensive industries but also financial, transport and other service sectors that are economically connected to fossil extraction, processing and distribution activities.

The comparison between 2030 and 2050 shows that the magnitude of change increases almost proportionally with the scale of technology deployment. This behaviour is coherent with the modelling assumption of a progressive expansion of NET-Fuels capacities over time. While the structure remains stable, expansion of NET-Fuels-related activities combined with contraction of fossil and energy-intensive sectors,

the absolute values increase as the technology approaches the maximum boundary of available processed biomass. Overall, the results indicate a targeted reallocation within the EU economy. The expansion of NET-Fuels activities is counterbalanced by reductions in fossil extraction, fossil fuel processing and selected upstream industrial sectors. The observed changes do not suggest a generalized contraction of economic output, but rather a transformation in the composition of production associated with the transition towards alternative fuel pathways.

Results presented for NET-Fuels effect in EU can be compared to results obtained for the economic impact on extra EU countries (RoW) in Annex I.

EU28 - NET-Fuels Technology Impact (2050)

7. Results II: Employment, Emissions and Resource Effects

The spillover indicator is called E in the model and includes heterogeneous stressors derived from the satellite matrix S (Exiobase). Each row retains its original physical unit of measure (e.g., kg for material extraction, kg CO₂-eq for GHG emissions, hours or persons for employment). Therefore, absolute values across stressors are not directly comparable; interpretation focuses on relative changes across scenarios.

Within the input–output framework adopted in this study, environmental impacts are calculated using the vector of environmental intensities *h* which represents emissions per unit of sectoral output. Total impacts are derived according to the standard Leontief formulation:

$$E = h \cdot (I - A)^{-1} \cdot y$$

7.1 NET-fuels Impact on Emissions

When comparing the general economic expansion to the 2020 baseline, total emissions increase in absolute terms by both 2030 and 2050, as effect of the overall increase of economic output mainly due to demand trend projections.

However, when we compare the 2030 and 2050 baseline scenarios to NET-Fuels scenarios, a decrease in total emissions is assessed. The total climate change impact decreases by approximately 1.60 MtCO₂eq in 2030 under NF relative to noNF and by approximately 24.4 MtCO₂eq in 2050. Direct air emissions are theoretically excluded from Net-Fuels emissions account as the integrated technologies use intermediate “flue” streams to generate products, as modeled in Task4.2 Life Cycle Inventory (LCI). The main GHG emissions connected with the technology scale-up refer to electricity consumption, which is associated to the electricity energy mix. Assuming a linear development of the mitigation effect due to Net-Fuels deployment between 2030 and 2050 from 27 plants to 500 plants, the technology would avoid approximately 260 Mt CO₂eq cumulatively over the period of time assuming a linear increase in NET-Fuels scale-up.

Table 11. NET-Fuels impact on GHG

GHG Emission in the NET-Fuel scenario			
2030		2050	
CO ₂ – combustion	-0.9 Mt	CO ₂ – combustion	-13.2 Mt
CH ₄ – non combustion:	-2.46 10 ⁻² Mt	CH ₄ – non combustion:	-0.37 × 10 ⁻¹ Mt
CO ₂ – non combustion:	-1.77 × 10 ⁻² Mt	CO ₂ – non combustion:	-0.29 Mt
Other gases	Negligible	Other gases	Negligible

Exiobase environmental satellite accounts display a list of GHG gases that can be quantified as physical emissions depending on economic output streams through a characterization matrix. Greenhouse gases assessed in this study include CO₂, N₂O, SF₆, CH₄, CO, which, in the case of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O, Exiobase categorizes between combustion and non-combustion sources.

In both 2030 and 2050, the introduction of NET-Fuels leads to a reduction mainly driven by CO₂ emissions from combustion processes. Reductions in CH₄ and N₂O are one to two orders of magnitude smaller, indicating that the mitigation effect at this stage is primarily associated with reduced fossil fuel combustion.

By 2050, CO₂ emissions from combustion decrease by -13.2 Mt. Additional reductions are observed in CO₂ from non-combustion processes - 0.3 Mt and CH₄ from non-combustion sources 0.4 Mt. Changes in N₂O

remain comparatively limited. Overall, the emission savings are primarily driven by reduced CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion, while secondary contributions arise from reduced methane emissions linked to upstream fossil supply chains.

The emission reductions can be directly linked to the output contraction observed in fossil-related sectors. Natural gas sectors exhibit one of the largest negative Δx values in the NF – noNF comparison, particularly by 2050.. Similarly, heavy fuel oil and fossil-based chemical sectors show declining output, further contributing to the decrease in combustion emissions.

Figure 11. Linear interpolation of CO₂eq savings between 2030 and 2050

An important element of the modelling framework concerns the treatment of carbon removal obtained by biochar production. In the present configuration, carbon credits are treated as an economic output of the NET-Fuels system and placed on the market as a tradable product. This modelling choice implies that the associated economic activity is included in sectoral output and contributes to the structural effects observed in the Δx results. However, the corresponding carbon removals are not directly subtracted from system emissions in the environmental assessment. In other words, biochar-derived removals are monetised and represented as a market product rather than being accounted for as negative emissions within the GWP calculation.

From the 2050 NF – noNF results, the additional output associated with NF_CarbonCredits in the EU28 amounts to approximately 0.046 MtCO₂eq yearly per plant that would have been accounted as carbon removals from biochar application in soil if the credits had been internalised as negative emissions rather than treated as a tradable product.

Overall, the emission results confirm that NET-Fuels induces a structural decarbonisation effect within the IO system. The contraction of fossil extraction and refining reduces combustion and non-combustion emissions, while the expansion of synthetic and bio-based fuel production operates within a progressively cleaner electricity backbone. The Leontief multiplier amplifies these effects across the supply chain, producing measurable reductions in GWP100 relative to the noNF scenario. At the same time, the explicit modelling of carbon credits as market output clarifies that part of the climate benefit is monetised rather than directly embedded as negative emissions in the assessment, ensuring methodological transparency and avoiding double counting of carbon removals.

7.2 NET-Fuels impact on materials

The results indicate that fossil resource extraction minimally decreases under the NF configuration relative to noNF mainly for indirect effect and taking into account NET-Fuels consumptions. Resources use changes were aggregated in five categories: Biomass, Fossil, Metal Ores, Non-metallic minerals and Water Consumption expressed in tonnes. When comparing the NF scenario with the 2020 baseline, total embodied material extraction increases due to demand trends projection for 2050. In 2030, Biomass increases by 11.73 kt, Fossil resources by 6.64 kt, Metal ores by 4.67 kt, and Non-metallic minerals by 23.00 kt relative to 2020. By 2050, these differences become larger: Biomass increases by 33.03 kt, Fossil by 18.15 kt, Metal ores by 12.63 kt, and Non-metallic minerals by 61.43 kt.

Subsequently, the study isolated the effect of NET-Fuels in the context of resource consumption expansion described above, by comparing NF with the noNF configuration for 2030 and 2050 obtaining the results presented in Table 12. In this context, NF scenario reduces the use of resources compared to the noNF scenario, suggesting that the indirect changes induced by NET-Fuels deployments exceed the use of biomass necessary for the technology functioning.

Table 12. NET-Fuels effect on resource consumption in kt (negative=consumption reduction)

Material Resource Use – Changes between NF and no NF scenario			
	2030	2050	
Biomass	-0.11	-1.91	kt
Fossil	-1.73	-26.07	kt
Metal Ores	-3.94	-0.65	kt
Non-metallic minerals	-3.98	-56.69	kt
Water Consumption	-0.05	-0.82	kt

In 2030 the comparison between the NF and noNF scenarios shows a reduction in all resource categories. The largest decrease concerns non-metallic minerals with -3.99 kt, followed by fossil resources which declines by -1.73 kt. More limited reductions are observed for biomass -0.11 kt, water consumption -0.05 kt and metal ores -0.04 kt. These variations can reflect the contraction of fossil-based energy supply chains and related upstream activities identified in the sectoral output analysis. However, in absolute terms, these changes remain very small when compared to the overall scale of the economic system and to the projected expansion of total output over the same period. They therefore represent marginal adjustments within a much larger structural evolution of the economy.

By 2050, the magnitude of the spillover increases in line with the larger scale of NF deployment. Non-metallic minerals decrease by -56.69 kt, fossil resources by -26.07 kt, biomass by -1.91 kt, water consumption by -0.82 kt, and metal ores by -0.66 kt. Although these reductions are more pronounced than in 2030, they remain limited relative to total material extraction volumes in the EU and global production system. The predominance of reductions in non-metallic minerals and fossil resources reflects structural adjustments in energy and industrial sectors, where lower fossil fuel extraction and reduced demand for mineral-intensive inputs propagate along inter-industry linkages. Overall, the results indicate that NF deployment generates modest but coherent improvements in material use, without substantially altering aggregate material demand trajectories. Direct NET-Fuels water consumption is thus compensated by indirect decrease of the overall system water consumption.

Overall, the material spillover results show two simultaneous dynamics. First, total material use increases between 2020 and future years due to system expansion. Second, conditional on that expansion, the introduction of NET-Fuels slightly reduces embodied material requirements relative to a noNF pathway.

Figure 12. NET-Fuels impact on resource consumption – 2030

Figure 13. NET-Fuels impact on resource consumption - 2050

7.3 NET-Fuels effect on Employment

Impacts on employment are derived from the labour extension of the IO model and therefore reflect total system effects. In this case, the vector h contains employment intensities expressed either in number of persons or in hours worked. The spillover results therefore capture both direct and indirect labour requirements embodied in the production structure.

Employment effects were calculated using the labour satellite accounts of the model. The results refer to the difference between the NF and noNF scenarios, isolating the structural “technology-only” effect of NET-Fuels. Values are representing either thousands of persons employed or thousands of hours worked, depending on the category, as indicated in the figures y axis. The results refer to total employment effects across the whole modelled system, including both the EU and the Rest of the World (RoW), due to global intersectoral linkages embedded in the input–output structure. While in general total employment increases in both 2030 and 2050 across all skill categories compared to the baseline scenario in 2020, if Net-fuel scenario is isolated, labour undergoes a contraction.

As shown in Figure 14 (2030), the introduction of NET-Fuels leads to a moderate but systematic reduction in employment compared to 2030 without NET-Fuels deployment. The largest decreases in 2030 are observed for medium-skilled male employment hours ($-3.44 \times 10^1 \times 10^3$ hours) and high-skilled male employment hours ($-2.25 \times 10^1 \times 10^3$ hours). Medium-skilled male employment in terms of persons decreases by $-1.63 \times 10^1 \times 10^3$ persons, while medium-skilled female employment hours decline by $-1.39 \times 10^1 \times 10^3$ hours. Reductions in low-skilled categories are comparatively smaller, for example $-4.32 \times 10^0 \times 10^3$ hours for low-skilled male employment hours and $-2.00 \times 10^0 \times 10^3$ persons for low-skilled male employment.

By 2050, the magnitude of employment effects increases substantially, as illustrated in Figure 15. The most pronounced reductions occur in medium-skilled male employment hours ($-5.33 \times 10^2 \times 10^3$ hours) and high-skilled male employment hours ($-3.51 \times 10^2 \times 10^3$ hours). Medium-skilled male employment in terms of persons decreases by $-2.52 \times 10^2 \times 10^3$ persons, while medium-skilled female employment hours decline by $-2.21 \times 10^2 \times 10^3$ hours. High-skilled female employment hours show a reduction of $-1.90 \times 10^2 \times 10^3$ hours, and high-skilled male employment in persons decreases by $-1.71 \times 10^2 \times 10^3$ persons. Reductions are observed across all skill levels and for both genders, indicating a system-wide adjustment rather than an isolated sectoral shift.

The larger reductions reported for male employment categories in both 2030 and 2050 reflect the labour composition included in the satellite labour accounts, rather than a behavioural gender-specific response to NET-Fuels. In sectors that contract most under the NF scenario, male employment shares are typically higher in the dataset structure, which leads to larger aggregated male employment effects. The model itself does not impose differential labour responses by gender, it propagates employment effects according to the sectoral gender profiles present in the input–output employment extension of Exiobase.

The employment results obtained in this assessment are aligned with recent evidence reported by the 2025 IRENA report “Renewable Energy and Jobs” (IRENA, 2026), which highlights that although renewable energy capacity additions reached record levels in 2024, employment growth slowed due to rising labour productivity, automation and economies of scale. This suggests that structural transformation towards more capital- and technology-intensive renewable systems does not necessarily translate into proportional job increases, in line with the patterns observed in the present IO-based analysis.

Figure 14. NET-Fuels impact on employment - 2030

Figure 15. NET-Fuels impact on employment - 2050

8. References

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9. ANNEX I - NET-Fuels economic effects on RoW

RoW – NET-Fuels Technology Impact (2050)

